

MECHANISMS OF DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIALLY ACTIVE CITIZENSHIP COMPETENCE IN STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: *In this article, the aim is to educate socially active citizens, well-rounded students with intellectual potential, to form and develop socially active civic competence, to train the young generation as professionals in the way of building a civil society and a democratic state in the country, as well as to develop their active citizenship position. It is illuminated through means of pedagogical influence.*

Keywords: *student, competence, reform, socially active citizenship, initiative, social - professionalism, perfection.*

At the heart of the reforms implemented in the continuous education system of our country, the most important task is to raise a socially active and mature generation. As a clear proof of this, the five important initiatives put forward by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on March 19, 2019 show that preschool education, secondary education, and higher education institutions are of great importance in raising socially active students.

On the basis of the reforms carried out by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is necessary to educate young people, who are today and tomorrow, on the basis of socially active civic competence. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, focused on the issue of raising socially active and well-rounded young people: "Improving the system of education and enlightenment, directing young people, who are the future of our country, to modern education, focusing on their interests receiving and supporting initiatives is the most important task facing the state and society, - they emphasize.

Addressing the Oliy Majlis on January 24, 2020, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan said: "As we aim to turn Uzbekistan into a developed country, we will achieve this not only through rapid reforms, science and innovation. For this, first of all, we need to educate the new generation of educated and qualified personnel who will be proactive reformers, who think strategically. It is important to mature as a socially active citizen.

Today, the formation of socially active civic competence among students studying in general secondary education institutions should first of all focus on approaches related to the concept of the concept of citizen, active citizenship. The purpose of socially active citizenship competence is to always encourage a person to be active in society, to participate in the political life of a democratic state, to have an active citizenship position. Nevertheless, the role of the state and society in a person's life is interpreted differently.

Decision No. 187, adopted by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on April 6, 2017, on the formation of socially active civic competences in students of general secondary schools, also focuses on general competencies related to basic and science. passed away. Formation of socially active civic competence in students of general secondary schools — "feeling

of commitment to events, events and processes in society and active participation in them, knowing and observing one's civic duties and rights, labor and citizenship it implies the formation of the abilities to acquire a legal culture and behavior in their relations. Because the education of the young generation, which is today and tomorrow of the state, has been the most urgent issue at different times.

The general secondary state education standard also focuses on the basic competencies in the formation of socially active citizenship competencies. In the formation of socially active civic competences in students, the competences of legal awareness and legal culture occupy an important place. The formation of knowledge, skills, skills and competence in students through the following levels (A1, A2, A2+, V1) of mastering the subject in the standard of general secondary education has a special place.

In the formation of socially active citizenship competence, students understand their rights and obligations through the A1 level, knowledge, skills and competencies are formed, such as being aware of the meaning of concepts such as duty, obligation, etiquette, ethics, citizen.

At the A2 level, students will have information about social and political reforms taking place in society, constitutional rights and duties, state power and its bodies, institutions of civil society, the basis of building a legal state, the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the opportunity to make an independent decision is revealed.

At the mastery level A2+, students-youth social activity together with having information about legal knowledge and skills, being able to explain the legal basis of social relations related to minors, events related to the rights and obligations of young people socially active qualities such as perception of events emerge.

At the B1 level, students-young people acquire knowledge about the content and signs of normative and legal documents related to all spheres of society, internationally recognized conventions and documents on the rights of young people. Also, qualities such as having information on the procedure for applying to executive bodies of state power and heads of educational institutions will be formed.

It is important to study not only the experience of our country, but also the experience of foreign countries in the development of socially active citizenship competence. Yu. V. Podlesnaya, one of the European scientists, research on the topic "Civil competence in modern society: political science aspects of formation and development" "expressing the existence of applied knowledge, skills and qualifications, also touched upon the theoretical issues of the development of civil competence of a person through his own activities.

A.M. Knyazev, one of the Russian scientists, divides the formation of a person into a citizen into three stages and justified the possibility of evaluating civic competence as a result of civic education as follows:

knowledge of the civil rights and obligations of a person, as well as the history of the country;

his destiny as a citizen, civil society, democratic state, system of civil rights and obligations;

civil duty and the rights and obligations of the citizen, the interests of the people and the state in the civil society, the civil behavior of the individual;

focusing on the civic values and confidence of a person;

The problem of the development of the qualities of civic competence has its solution in the scientific literature, but taking into account the purely individual acquisition of knowledge in students through the development of socially active civic competence as a subjective quality of a person, the subjective nature of teaching. The need to develop skills and qualifications depending on motives, attitude to the subject of education, abilities, personal qualities and experience of the learner requires an individual approach in the development of civic competence.

If the knowledge about the formation of socially active civic competences is taught in the general secondary education system, in the higher education system, the development of socially active civic competences in students and the development of students in the way of building a democratic and legal state in the country Increasing knowledge, active participation in the activities of civil society institutions is demonstrated.

In our opinion, the following goals can be achieved in the development of socially active citizenship competence through the tasks mentioned above:

Socially active civic competence students develop the skills of building a democratic state, self-governing bodies, civil society institutions, forming legal culture and legal consciousness, socially active citizenship and participation in political processes;

Socially active civil competence education of students develops important qualities such as democracy, freedom of speech, unconditional obedience to the laws of the country, upbringing in the spirit of national values (human dignity, individuality, generosity, endurance, humanitarianism, freedom, generosity).

To sum up, the development of socially active civic competence in young people and the education of a mature generation are being proven in the reforms carried out in our country. On the basis of the above-mentioned definitions, we call it socially active citizenship competence, which means that young people feel a sense of involvement in the events taking place in the life of society, and apply their knowledge and skills in practice regarding their rights and obligations in building a democratic state and civil society. is said to acquire an active citizenship position.

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